

THE DETERMINANT FACTORS POSITIVELY EFFECT PERFORMANCE OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOR IN IGBO NIGERIA AND MEDIATION ROLE OF INTENTION

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Abstract

This study focuses on describing the field of entrepreneurship activity (EA) in terms of the performance of women's entrepreneurial behaviour and intention to do business in Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to examine the determinants factors that influence women's entrepreneurial behavior and the mediating role of women's entrepreneurial intention. The theory of planned behavior and other theories are used. The conceptual framework is built to explained the variables, and also all concepts are briefly explained before emphasizing the relevant concepts of the study. In this study, we used a pilot study of demographic respondent on 70 women entrepreneurs in Imo state and partial least squares structure equation modelling (PLS-SEM) to test hypotheses on the sample of 362 women entrepreneurs in Abia and Imo states in Igbo Nigeria. The results of this study show that attitudes, education, financial capital, perceived family business, social cultural and self-efficacy positively and significantly influence women's outcomes in entrepreneurial behavior and women's entrepreneurial intention, which significantly partially mediates the relationship between all the variables.

Keywords: Business support, Nigerian higher education companies and government policy makers to unlock the potential of women's entrepreneurship.

INTRODUCTION

In a globalized world, entrepreneurship management plays an important role in the sustainability of business start-ups (Lammers, et al., 2022), this study understands the relationship between entrepreneurship activities, and the performance of women entrepreneurial behavior and women entrepreneurial intention in SMEs. The constant pressures competition on globalization and technological change make the study of entrepreneurial activity very important. It is a process of creating value and pursuing opportunities for growth. Women entrepreneurs play a key role in entrepreneurial performance and the economy development by promoting job creation, poverty reduction, wealth creation and nation-builder (Ribeiro, et al., 2022). It is also there is a driving force that drives female to develop in the global economy.

A growing body of evidence supports the link between women's entrepreneurial intentions and performance in entrepreneurial behavior. This helps women start businesses as entrepreneurs (Lakhan, et., al, 2021). (Chapter 1) provides an introduction to the subject and a brief overview of the study, as well as a characterization of how Nigerian women ran the family business before the colonial period. ((Arrival of white men in Nigeria). The chapter begins with a brief

background of research in this area. This chapter includes background study as well as the problems statement, research objectives or goals, research questions, and research significance, scope of the study. The chapter concludes with definitions of key terms of the study, the following section describes the most important concepts related to this task.

Problem Statement

The total population of women in Nigeria consists of more than 50%, according to (Amadi, & Adim, (2020), out of this population, only 35% are women entrepreneurs. A small percentage as this has shown the imbalance and yet the same group of people have contributed to businesses that offer flexibility and innovativeness which are critical to the flourishing of the economy. Igbo women characterized in keeping their families group in the economy large sustained by producing goods and services and also become very lively in the agriculture, trades, and other economic activities (Wole-Abu, N. A., 2018).

The coming of Whiteman, which is the pre-Colonial age has destroyed all the opportunity from Igbo women in the society and also deny them access to medium and large scales loans, access to cash crop incentives, technology and innovation (Ezeanya-Esiobu, C. (2019). Moreover, these contributed the ideas of some women continue depending on the husband financial welfare (Okolie, et., al., 2021). Women entrepreneurs in Igbo Land face several cultural and developmental issues like: Lack of family support business

Lack of sufficient financial capital,

Limited education/ knowledge

Social cultural constraints,

Lack of Self-efficacy.

RO1: To determine the effect of attitude, perceived family support business, financial capital, education, social-cultural and self-efficacy on women entrepreneurial behavior performances.

RO2: To investigate the impact of attitude, perceived family support business, financial capital, education, social-cultural and self-efficacy on women entrepreneurial intention.

RO3: To analyze the effect of women entrepreneurial intention on women entrepreneurial behavior performances.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept in the field of entrepreneurship caught the researcher's attention in the current time women's entrepreneurial behavior. This chapter will highlight some of the previous research conducted in this area, and also review the former literature on women entrepreneurship and performances of women entrepreneurial behavior (PWEB), and women's intention (WEI) which become important to understand the relationship of the constructed base on women entrepreneurs in Nigeria with latest available data. Moreover, the existing literature includes empirical and theoretical will help to synthesize the theories.

This literature review assisted to understand the comparison differences of the relevant variables to get knowledge of the context of this study, and the chapter also reported on the framework of the study and the rationality and the reasoning, based on which the hypotheses were developed. In addition, it gives the problem and challenges facing women entrepreneurs in Nigeria.

This chapter also describes the theory of planned behavior, with the extension of the theory of reasoned action, developed subsequent Ajzen I, 1980; Heiny, Jennifer, et al. 2019), arguments, most notably through the inclusion of perceived towards a behavior are evaluated within the context of subjective norms and perceived behavioral control.

Concerning perceived behavioral control, individuals assess their ability regarding the issues /ease in performing a given behavior. This assessment is reflective of experience and is based on perceptions about resource availability.

Concept of Women Entrepreneurs

The concept of (WE), according (Aich, D. 2020), the concept of (WE) emphasizes that a woman who takes responsibility to organize and manage the resources of their enterprises and bears all the risks in expectations of deriving gain can be termed a woman entrepreneur. This definition depicts women entrepreneurs to be aware of decision makers and managers (Zohora, F.2022). Females who are selected to pursue the challenging role of an entrepreneur have the ambition to desire the fulfilment of their need to achieve and be independent.

Women entrepreneurship creates actions, especially in industry, this activity empowers them economically and helps them to contribute hugely to economic growth. (Simon, & Marathe 2023). (Rastogi, Baral, & Banu, 2022). Whether women are engaged in small or medium-scale business activities or the self-employed or employed areas, female entrepreneurial actions are not only a method for economic continuation. However, they have the positive social consequence that concern female and their social surroundings United Nations Industrial Development Organization (Soomro, Bahadur Ali, Sadia Anwar, & Aftab Hussin Rajar 2019).

Challenges of Female Entrepreneurship in Nigeria

Nigerian Entrepreneurships reported that they have been frequently harassed by government officials who extort money from their businesses (Resnick, et., al. 2023), (Beegle, & Christiaensen 2019), (Driscoll, B, 2020). Poor infrastructure like bad roads, water shortage, and inadequate water supply are some of the issues plaguing the private sector and their business challenges in gaining bank credits and from other financial institutions (Abubakar, Binna, 2019).

General government lack interest in the growth of entrepreneurship. Many countries in the world embrace the improvement of entrepreneurship development. A lot of entrepreneurs lack managerial skills to help in planning and organizing their enterprises (Osita- Ejikeme & Amah 2021). Inability to recruit and retain good employees and in turn possibly good employees are reluctant to work with the private sector because they lack job Low average labour productivity Unemployment (Nkansah-Dwamena, E. 2022). Several authors have commented on barriers

and challenges facing women entrepreneurs such as (Sagara, Y., 2021), (Das, K. C. 2022), (Wralsen, et. al., 2021), (Selamat, & Endut, 2020), (Politaj, & koza, 2020), (Said, et. al., 2020) (Dana, et. al., 2021), (Krocak, et. al., 2020). The economic activities of most women are based on the self-employed sector of the economy both in rural and urban areas. The reason may be due to entry into the self-employed sector is easy, and it is allowed to all categories of people. It includes hairdressers, fashion designers, beauty and skin sailors, crafts making etc. The self-employed sector is characterized by reliance on indigenous resources, family ownership of enterprise, labor-intensive and adapted technology, unregulated and competitive markets and skills that can be acquired outside the business professional educational system (Dave, M. et., al. 2022).

Most women are predominantly in the self-employed sector because it does not require any minimum level of education as in the business professional areas; second, they can combine their activities with domestic responsibility and third is that it requires little capital to establish most businesses in the self-employed sector (Kenny S, V., 2019). Women entrepreneurs in Nigeria face similar challenges and constraints to their counterparts than other developing countries. Over the last few decades, the significant contribution of women in sustaining the socio-economic well-being of their families had been taken for granted and even neglected by society (Sajjad, et. al., 2020).

Characteristics of Women Entrepreneurs

Female entrepreneurs frequently have a particular personality. They value independence and autonomy (Keling, Yap, & Ho, 2022), (Bastian, et. al., 2023). They acquire energy and a high need for accomplishment. Female entrepreneurs obtain a strong internal position of control. They became aware of the change as an opportunity and willing to take accurate risks.

They are commonly having social skills and acquire a balance between insight the ideas (Tonidandel, et. al., 2022), (Hynes, & Block, 2022), (Adaeze Eucheria Ekwochi, 2020), stated that female business mainly has the related typical feature and motivations with male business holders. Females in the economic class find it a problem to have their want in the working position (Bullough, et., al. 2022). (Female needs are ravenous), so far it turning to entrepreneurship, it will help them to bring their favourable circumstances.

Entrepreneurship has made females capable of economic actions and increased autonomy resources foundation. This benefit helps women to enhance financial support for themselves and all so improve their social status and make decision ability. Female entrepreneurship appreciates some strength benefits such as ownership of two-fold typical features (entrepreneurial and women characteristics which gives them an amazing ability to carry out their role as entrepreneurs (Chen, et., al., 2022).

The following characteristic are Adaptability, Innovativeness/ creativity, Strength, Ability to think fast, Ability to endure, Accountability and credibility and Managerial Skills.

1 Adaptability, female is seen to be easier to adapt to family life work than male matches (Thoits, P. A. 2022), (Naukkarinen, & Gordon, 20220, (Alaei, et. al., 2022), (Jolly, et. al., 2022).

They can adjust to the different situations of culture, behavioural averages, skilled networks, and family relationships all affect the attitudes of female entrepreneurship. Hens adaptability improves entrepreneurship and female balance nature makes it possible to adapt to their surroundings better than their male counterparts (Boutkhil, S. 2022).

Benefits of Women Entrepreneurship

Several benefits have been reported about women entrepreneurship, some of the benefits reported in the literature according to (Meyer and Hamilton, 2020). It is plentiful vivid that entrepreneurship is significant for economic development, productivity, innovation and employment, and huge nations have made entrepreneurship specific policy first concern.

1. Women entrepreneurship activities have been acknowledged as the significant essential feature in managerial, economic growth, performance and wealth generation. According to (Bullough, et. al., 2022).
2. Precisely they choose the hours to work as well as how much to pay if he would take a vacation or not (Abuhusseini, T., 2022).
3. Gives a greater achievement feasibility important revenue rewards than employed by someone else.
4. It brings the ability to be engaged in the whole operation of the job to plan the designs and establishment sales and customer feedback.
5. They always show importance of being the person in charge.
6. They contribute opportunities to build fairness, in the feature or reputation of the next generation.
7. It establishes the opportunity for someone to donate.
8. Greater pioneers of female entrepreneurs sees their local revenue through innovation of the whole society (Alsheikah, A. 2022), (Mashapure, et. al., 2022).

It is an incentive for economic changes and development and also it boosts one's capital output and money. Moreover, it introduces comprise changes in the society of new business structure that result in huge contribution output of nations productivity (Khan, et. al., 2022). Market fulfil human needs by innovation and creativity, developing new products and services which is encouraged by entrepreneurs (Fallah, & Soori, 2022).

Entrepreneurship through its method of innovation builders, more ventures created, and fresh job opportunity formed, and it reduces the unemployment rate. With all these advantages, the promotion of wealth was distributed (Chatterjee, et. al., 2022). It's not the primary reason someone pursues entrepreneur activities; it also plays important role in nation's economy. The business environment is highly dynamic and hence controls the operations and activities of business ventures (Kang, H.Y. 2022).

The understanding of the dynamic and the effect of the environment on women's entrepreneurial development is very important for policymaking (Victor Chidiebere, et. al., 2022), saw family influence as the antecedent of women entrepreneurial developments, included infrastructure, legal, regulatory, economic and socio-cultural variables such as rapid and threatening change, one's family, school and work environment as the environmental factors that can affect women entrepreneurs (Pospisil, & Zavodna, 2022), further classified these factors into 'push' and 'pull' factors. Looked at the environmental factors from the perspective of the developmental setting that stimulates the local market.

Attitude

The general definition of attitudes cognate both positive or negative belief and feelings about objects or things (Fu, M., et. al, 2022), (Ede, et. al., 2021), (Nutbeam, & Mereish, 2022), (Trajano, et., al., 2022), (Rastogi, et. al., 2022). Attitudes are embrace through builder, classical and social learning that are stable and durable to categories of individual. So far attitudes are enduring traits that intent important behaviors that study women attitudes and belief about entrepreneurs which could give information about the social images of women who engage in the business. According to (Alhnaity, H., 2021), stated that an individual can be able to start-up and chase entrepreneurial action when the intention is increase in the relationship to a specific opportunity. (Pasricha, & Singh, , 2020), suggested that the entrepreneurial cycle in the business begin with the creation of women entrepreneurial intention. Which means the women intent to starts-up a company, is from personal ambition of self-employment, higher level of her own independent rather begin jobseeker.

In addition, previous study has factors that are affecting women entrepreneurial attitude to start-up and achievement their goals (Mazhar, et., al. 2022), (Kovaleva, et., al. 2023). Such factors are systemic support, financial access, information and social network which is consider as perceived support, perceived constraints and close support. But current study concern is to investigates the determinant factors that are positively affect women entrepreneurial intention and behavioural aspect. In general, individuals will hold a positive attitude towards business ownership, if they perceive that other people important to them evaluate business ownership positively. In fact, a widely held view is that family background/childhood experiences, exposure to others in business, and previous job experiences influence the development of entrepreneurial-related attitudes (Castleberry Steven B. et. al., 2020).

Many researchers have used this factor in their study such as, (Plonitkov, et., al., 2020), (Tjokrosaputro, et. al., 2020), (Jiatong, et., al., 2021), (Anwar, et. al., 2021), also mentioned that these intentions are the result of attitudes developed through experience and personal characteristics (Ajzen, 1996), (Wang, J., 2020), (Hassan, A., et. al, 2020), and (Baluku, M. M., et., al. 2020). The current study used to know how positively attitude affect women entrepreneurial intention and behavior. However, the attitudes towards business ownership will mediate the relationship between prior family business experience and entrepreneurial intentions, since the TPB would predict that they will positively lead to entrepreneurial intentions. Attitude towards behavior (ATB), according to Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) attitude towards behavior is "person's good or bad assessment toward performing or not to perform

certain behavior”. The attitude differs from the characteristics related to the nature of the assessment by a particular intention (Armitage and Conner, 2001). In the entrepreneurial intention studies, attitude towards behavior has proven to be an important factor in influencing the intention positively (Sweida, et., al., 2022). (Hasan., et., al., 2022). Attitude toward behavior has a direct and strongly positive impact on entrepreneurial intentions. It is therefore necessary to make efforts to change one's personal behavior (Damodharan, & Ahmed, 2022).

Financial Capital

Access to financial capital defined resources as tangible and intangible forms of property which are steady permanently with the enterprises (Nama, & Kanungo, 2023). The recognition of access and obtaining of financial resources are detracting to develop of any entrepreneurial venture (Williams, M.2023). To improve performances, development oriented female entrepreneurs need financial resources, unluckily acquisition financial resources is a greater challenge for female entrepreneurs than male entrepreneurs (Simon, & Marathe, 2023), (Lisowska, & Leszczynski, 2023).

The capacity of female owned business to access financial has become the issues of consideration, some researcher takes it as an argument over past fifteen years, (Alene, E.T., 2020), (Rudhumbu, et. al., 2020), (Orobia, et., al, 2020), (Noor, & Isa, 2020), (Umejiaku, R.I., 2020), (Lauto, et. al., 2022). Such gender dissimilarity in access to money someone own capital has become studied widely. Women need fairness and justice, equality and opportunity, equal access, equal treatment, equal sharing and allocation of resources, and bring everyone to the same level regardless of the tools they already have or don't have (Mashapure, et. al., 2022), (Ishak, et al., (2021), indicated that regardless of the widespread recognition that female entrepreneurship plays an important part in financial development, their level of development has remained on a downward trend.

A global cruel reality is that women constitute larger percentage of most economies but remain particularly downgraded and frequently on the receiving end of male-controlled prejudgments. In countries like Nigeria, most district cultures treat women as second-class citizens, which is believed to presuppose women to be women (Ndlela, W.H.Z., 2022).

Businesswomen agree to face undue hardships throughout their business to (Johnson, et., al., 2019), (Margaret., et., al, 2019), (Erin, et., al, 2020). The efficiency of gender-based federal procurement policies in United states, American government has targeted 23% of its annual half-trillion dollar spend to SMs and 5%of its female owned businesses (Abdelfattah, et., al, 2022).

To accomplish these policy aims, Congress authorized a several of programs that supply contacts for contest particularly between businesses especially as worthy by each program. Between these programs the female –Owned Small Business (WOSB) Federal Contract Program is exclusively interest to research (Orser, Barbara, Allan, and Julie, 2019). Financial capital in women entrepreneurs in cottage, micro small, and medium sole proprietors. Proof from the financial area in Bangladesh 2010- 2018), (Shoma, C. D. 2019).

Perceived Family Business Support

While no universal definition of a family business provides a definition that supports the role that “family” plays in business ownership (Morsy, H., 2020), define a family business as a business governed and/or managed with the intention to shape and pursue the vision of the business held by a dominant coalition controlled by members of the same family or a small number of families in a manner that is potentially sustainable across generations of the family or families.

The author (Jaskiewicz, et. a., 2020), (Koellner, et. al., 2023), suggests that the family business plays a great role in the career choices of individual family members, and in particular the children of family members associated with the business. In fact, the attitudes and subjective standard related to this career choice may be reflective of this influence.

Thus, the attitudinal and behavioral mechanisms within the family business can shape or influence subsequent entrepreneurial. Research in family business examines the means by which family-owned businesses handle success (Telling and Goulding, 2020).

Family involvement, family structure determines the types of businesses women can enter (Bauweraets, et. al. 2022). He also believes that married women have a double influence. That is, close relatives and the husband's family. Given the multitasking nature of women as wives and sometimes the breadwinners of the household, and the unique characteristics of women that inhibit their participation in business, it is important to improve the environment to encourage women's participation in economic development. We need to make it possible and create an environment that makes it possible for women to achieved their goals in their ventures.

Previous researchers comment on perceived family support business challenges and issues of loan that affecting women entrepreneurial intention (Qazi, et. al., 2022), (Ahmed, & Usman, 2020), (Al-Mamary, et., al, 2020), (Nowinski, et., al, 2020), (Neneh, B.N., 2020), (Saleh, P.F., Ali, et., al, 2021), (Mujahid, et.al., 2020). Another study emphasized on the impact the individual intention has been very important in entrepreneurial venture especial. (Dowling, et., al, 2019), said that an entrepreneurial intention coursed along with following applied entrepreneurial activities that bring great impact on student to search for entrepreneurship. The researchers consider the role that family business plays in encouraging future entrepreneurial inclinations (Hahn, et. al., 2021), (USADHA, et. al, 2022).

This is certainly understandable, since the nature of family ownership and succession lead to interesting (and at times troubling) challenges. Another research conducted to find out the influence of family business experience and identified that family experiences constitute a powerful socializing influence on the values, attitudes, and behaviors people adopt over the course of their lives. According to (Yasir, et. al., 2021), stated that consistent with theory of planned behavior, results suggest significant direct and indirect effects of prior family business exposure on entrepreneurial intent, through the mediation variables of attitudes towards business ownership, perceived family support business and entrepreneurial ESE.

Business establishment on the part of female can affect families, the family support towards the business person is the basic element. (Canovi, et. al, 2022), indicates that women are double as likely to start their own business, if the husband is already a business ownership (Dewitt, et. al., 2022), observed that 50% of the female entrepreneurs have family support who had run businesses. Demand this percentage to be near to 64%.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes all methods of conducting research and highlights the approaches researchers use to achieve the goals set at the beginning of the chapter. This study used quantitative methods to observe research. The aim of the current study is to explore the core factors that positively influence women's entrepreneurial intention and the relationships between all variables, if it influences the entrepreneurial behavior of women in SMEs. The chapter begins with layers of research onion diagrams that describe research philosophies, approaches, method choices, techniques, and procedures. Followed by a strategy that refers to an overall action plan that guides researchers on how to conduct systematic research, a research design framework is divided into stages to describe each stage of the research design framework.

BRIEF EXPLANATION OF ONIONS DIAGRAM

Research Onions Diagram.

Philosophy: It refers to the set of principles concerning the worldview or stance from which the research is conducted. It is usually studied in terms of ontology and epistemology. Here, ontology refers to the authenticity of the information and how one understands its existence, whereas epistemology refers to the valid information required for the research and how one can obtain it. Philosophical positions used in academic studies are often divided into positivism, interpretivism, pragmatism and realism, where positivism assumes that knowledge is independent of the subject being studied, and interpretivism claims that individual observers have their own perception and understanding of reality. Hence positivist studies are often more scientific and result in testing phenomena, whereas interpretivism studies are often qualitative

Approach of Theory Development: Once the researcher has chosen the appropriate methodology; the research onion suggests that an appropriate research must be picked. The deductive approach is not where you can explain theory by observation, quantitative research should have explained base on empirical observation and theory generated on conceptual and theoretical structure. Deductive method has a lot of benefit in research example, (1) It has feasibility justification in the relationship concepts and variables. (2) It has capacity to measure quantitative to generate research findings to a certain range. Deductive approach investigates a known theory or phenomenon and test if the theory is valid in given or it starts with a specific hypothesis development based on the literature review that has been observed by the researcher, and gradually tries to test this hypothesis and check if it holds in particular contexts. Several researchers on emphases on it (Alturki, R. (2021), (Ng, M. S., Hall, D., Schmailzl, M., Linner, T., & Bock, T. (2022). (Politou, A. S., Pastore, A., & Temussi, P. A. (2022). (Navasardyan, S., & Ohanyan, M. (2022), (Alturki, R. (2021).

Methodological Approach of (Choices of Method): The research onion suggests mono-method, mixed method and multi-method as possible choices for conducting research. The mono-method comprises only one method for the study. The mixed method is based on the use of two or more methods of research and commonly refers to the use of qualitative and quantitative methodology. Finally, the multi-method uses a wider selection of methods.

Approach of Strategies: After this, the researcher is expected to devise the strategy of the study. The research onion suggests that strategies can include action research, experimental research, interviews, surveys, case study research or a systematic literature review. The strategy is chosen based on the data required for the research and the purpose of the study.

Approach (Time Horizons): It refers to the time frame of the research. Generally, observations can be of two types based on time horizons, namely cross-sectional and longitudinal. The cross-sectional data is used when all observations are for a single point of time such as in most surveys. Longitudinal data, in contrast, implies the observations for a particular variable that are available for several years, quarters, months or days.

Data Collection and Analysis: This is the final layer of the research onion that consists of the techniques and procedures used. It is used to clearly explain the ways and purposes of the research conducted. At this stage, the researcher is expected to choose between the primary and secondary data and between qualitative and quantitative data collected from different sources. Data is considered the central piece in the research onion framework.

The research onions of Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill provide high-quality knowledge of how researchers would write their papers, detailing their research goals and the approaches that ultimately led them to arrive at their results.

This current researcher used philosophy - positivist, deductive, quantitative, research experiments, cross-sectional and data collection, and data analysis used variables such as attitudes, financial capital, and perceived family support. To test the determinants that influence the performance of women's entrepreneurial behavior in Igbo Nigeria between business, education/knowledge, sociocultural and self-efficacy, and relationships between all variables (IV & DV) it is also a mediator intended to examine the effects of this diagram is described in detail later in this chapter.

DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Demographics:

Descriptive statistical Analysis

Table 1

Statistics							
		1. What is your age range?.....(years)	2. What is your marital status?	3. Educational level?	4. How long have you been doing business or in others words what level of experience are you?	5. How do you categorize yourself?	6. What are the methods through which skills are acquired in running the business?
N	Valid	71	71	71	71	71	71
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2

1. What is your age range?.....(years)					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid		1	1.4	1.4	1.4
	18- 28	12	16.9	16.9	18.3
	28 - 38	25	35.2	35.2	53.5
	38 - 48	26	36.6	36.6	90.1
	48 - 58	6	8.5	8.5	98.6
	59 & above	1	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	71	100.0	100.0	

Table 3

2. What is your marital status?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid		1	1.4	1.4	1.4
	Divorced	5	7.0	7.0	8.5
	Married	31	43.7	43.7	52.1
	Prefer not to be	3	4.2	4.2	56.3
	Single	30	42.3	42.3	98.6
	widowed	1	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	71	100.0	100.0	

Table 4

3. Educational level?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid		1	1.4	1.4	1.4
	Degree and above	54	76.1	76.1	77.5
	Diploma	8	11.3	11.3	88.7
	No Education	1	1.4	1.4	90.1
	Primary	2	2.8	2.8	93.0
	Secondary	5	7.0	7.0	100.0

Figure 1

Concerning the age ranges, it was identified that respondents in the range of 38-48 gave more responses obtaining 36.6% followed by respondents in the range 28-38 has 35.2%, while 18-28 has 16.9%, 48 -58 has 8.5%%, and 59 above which is the last number has 1.4 %, as shown in the diagram.

Figure 2

Regarding in the marital status, the highest marital number held by the respondents were married, followed by single, divorce, prefer not to marry, and widowed.

Figure 3

In relation to education, the highest education level held by respondents were Degree and above, followed by diploma, Secondary, primary level and no education.

Measurement Model

Confirmatory Factors Analysis (CFA)

In a statistical examination of data, the measurement model is what is used to graphically show the links that exist between the actual data and the latent variables. For the purpose of determining the validity and reliability of the scale, criteria such as "factor loadings, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)" were used. When attempting to establish whether or not a model

Loadings, Reliability, and Convergent Validity.

	Loading	CA-rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
ATT	0.888	0.897	0.918	0.692
EKL	0.882	0.939	0.911	0.672
FCL	0.895	0.914	0.922	0.704
PFS	0.881	0.884	0.913	0.678
SCI	0.900	0.900	0.923	0.667
SEF	0.861	0.865	0.906	0.707
WEB	0.877	0.884	0.910	0.670
WEI	0.868	0.877	0.905	0.655

Fornell and Larcker

	ATT	EKL	FCL	PFS	SCI	SEF	WEB	WEI
ATT	0.832							
EKL	0.643	0.820						
FCL	0.726	0.396	0.839					
PFS	0.753	0.546	0.654	0.824				
SCI	0.719	0.582	0.679	0.821	0.817			
SEF	0.822	0.670	0.656	0.813	0.739	0.841		
WEB	0.731	0.644	0.669	0.723	0.747	0.783	0.819	
WEI	0.635	0.638	0.679	0.702	0.781	0.745	0.803	0.809

The work of Fornell and Larcker (1981) has come under fire in recent years, and this criticism suggests that the authors' results should not be relied upon to identify cases of poor discriminant validity in the current research environment. (Henseler et al., 2015). Researcher Hensler et al. (2015), (Aplin-Houtz, et. al., 2023), developed a new approach for assessing discriminant validity. Their technique is based on the multitrait-multimethod matrix. From what they say, "The heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT).

CONCLUSION

The research was fundamentally concerned with investigating the impact of women entrepreneurial intention on the performances of women entrepreneurial behavior in entrepreneurship industry activity in Igbo Nigeria. The results showed that the correlation between performances of women entrepreneurial behavior activities was influenced by women entrepreneurial intention. The primary data were obtained from a female entrepreneur's survey involving 362 females of Abia and Imo states in Igbo Nigeria. Based on the results of the quantitative analysis of the structural model, performances of women entrepreneurial behavior and women entrepreneurial intention are directly and positively related to all exogenous constructs.

In general, these activities will increase the value of entrepreneurship organizations, if women will be more determined, committed, creative, innovative and willing to take risks in their businesses. The finding vividly shows that performances of women entrepreneurial behavior are positively influenced by all exogenous constructs which are attitude, financial capital, perceived family support business, social-cultural, and self-efficacy intention on entrepreneurship activity in Igbo Nigeria.

The study shows that women entrepreneurial intention played a mediating role in the relationship between performances of women entrepreneurial behavior and exogenous variable activities. In fact, the theory of planned behavior, women always feel motivated to bring value to their firms, when they see like the organization is supporting them. Women are highly expected to be more determined and committed to some positive socially sustainable environmental activities that inspired them to create new ideas. The conceptual starting point of the current study provides a new

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